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Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining bilim saviyasi rivojlanishida musiqaning ahamiyati

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining bilim saviyasi rivojlanishida musiqaning ahamiyati va amaliy fanlarda amaliy mashg'ulotlarning o'quvchining mustaqil izlanuvchanlik va yaratuvchanlik qobiyatini rivojlantirishdagi beqiyos o'rni va boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ijodiy qobiliyatini rivojlantirishning ijtimoiy psixologik xususiyatlari, didaktik usul va metodalrdan foydalanish haqida ilmiy-amaliy tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *O'qituvchi, maktab, ta'lim, ijodkorlik, didaktik, usul, metod, kreativ, pedagogika, shaxs, faollik, o'quvchi, boshlang'ich ta'lim, qobiliyat.*

KIRISH

Yangi O'zbekistonning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy taraqqiyotida xalqimizning hayoti, davlatimizning siyosiy faoliyatida tub o'zgarishlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Yangi O'zbekistonda xalqimiz o'zining buyuk kelajagini yaratmoqda. Uni yaratishda

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ulug' ajdodlarimiz – buyuk pedagog –faylasuflar, din arboblari, mutasavvif donishmandlar, ulug' allomalarning ta'limotlarini o'rganish sari yo'l ochildi. Asrlar mobaynida xalqimiz saqlab kelayotgan milliy, umuminsoniy qadriyatlarni ilmiy tadqiq qilib rivojlantirishga yangi imkoniyatlar yaratildi.

Davlat taraqqiyoti va jamiyat ravnaqi ko'p jihatdan uning intellektual potensiali bilan belgilanadi. Chunki, ilmiy potensiali yuqori darajada rivojlangan mamlakat barcha sohalarda doimo ilg'or bo'ladi. Shuningdek, davlat ta'lim standartlarida belgilangan bilim, ko'nikma va malakalari doirasidan tashqari yangi zamonaviy fanlar va axborot texnologiyalariga doir bilimlarni o'zlashtirish zamon talabiga aylanmoqda.

Hozirda boshlang'ich ta'lim tizimining asosiy vazifalari o'quvchilarni har tomonlama barkamol shaxs etib tarbiyalash maqsadida ularga mustaqil fikrlash, o'zligini anglash, bilimlarni o'rganishda, maktabda va maktabdan tashqari ishlarda faollik, boy ma'naviyatimiz va qadriyatlarimizni o'rgatish, o'z shaxsidagi "men"ini tanitish, yuksak axloqiy fazilatlar va estetik ruhda tarbiyalashdan iborat.¹

MUHOKAMA VA NATIJALAR

Ijodiy qobiliyatlar muammosi psixologiya fanida qiziqarli va ma'lum darajada tadqiq qilingan muammolardan biridir. Bu muammo yuzasidan qadimdan to shu kunga qadar izlanishlar olib borganlar. Insonning imkoniyatlarini o'rganishga sharq mutafakkirlari (Farobiy, Beruniy, Abu Ali ibn Sino),, Rossiya psixologlari (B.M.Teplov, B.G.Ananev, N.V.Kuzmina, S.L.Rubinshteyn, A.G.Kovalev,

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V.N.Myasishev), G'arb olimlari (A.Bine, T.Simon, F.Galton, V.Shtern, U.Ollport, K.Rodjers) kabilar katta xissa qo'shganlar. Ushbu muammo ustida Uzbekiston psixolog olimlari (E.G'oziey, R.Gaynutdinov, M.G.Davletshin, B.R.Kodirov, V.A.Tokareva va boshqalar) ham izlanish olib borganlar.

Ijodkorlik deganda insonning yangilik yaratish, muammolarni yechishga qaratilgan ijodiy qobiliyati tushuniladi. Uning tag zahirida orginallik, amaliylik, noodatiylik va erkinlik yotadi.

Shuningdek, ijodiy fikrlash muayyan masala yuzasidan har tomonlama fikrlash, bir nuqtaga turli rakursdan qaray olishni anglatadi.

Ijodiy fikrlash- bu shunday fikrlashki, natijada ma'lum bir muammoni tubdan yangi yoki takomillashtirilgan yechimini topish demakdir.

J.Guilfordning fikriga ko'ra ijodiy fikrlashning xususiyatlari quydagilar: O'ziga xoslik, g'ayrioddiy g'oyalar; Semantik moslashuvchanlik-ob'ektni turli nuqtai nazardan ko'rish qobiliyati; Majoziy moslashuvchanlik-ob'ektning yashirin tomonlarini ko'rish uchun idrokini o'zgartirish qobiliyati; Noma'lum vaziyatda turli g'oyalarni ishlatish qobiliyati deb sanab o'tgan.

“Inson, o'zi va ruhiyati orasidagi hamda o'zi va boshqa birov orasidagi mavjud narsani tadqiq etishda bor imkoniyatni ishlatib muntazam ravishda mashq qildirib turish kerak. Buni u haqiqat vositalarini egallashda sabot bilan yo o'qitish va murabbiylik usullari yoki bahs va himoya usullari bilan amalga oshirilishi zarur” deb yozadi, Abu Nasr Farobiyning Fozil odamlar shahri kitobida².

Biz boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini o'qitish va tarbiyalashning eng muhim

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nazariy va amaliy jihatlarini bilishimiz kerak. Buning uchun avvalo, quyidagi psixologik - pedagogik muammolarni tushunib olmog'imiz lozim:

- o'quvchi shaxsining psixologik rivojlanganlik darajasi;
- o'quvchi shaxsining shakllanishi va o'quv-mehnat faoliyati mazmuni;
- o'quvchi shaxsi tabiatining tavsifnomasi va ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari.

O'quvchi shaxsining psixologik rivojlanganlik darajasini to'la yoritish uchun biz uning rivojlanish xususiyatlari borasida muayyan ma'lumotlarga ega bo'lishimiz lozim.

Biz faoliyatimiz davomida o'quvchilarning psixologik rivojlanishi yosh xususiyatlari bilan chambarchas bog'liqligini kuzatamiz. Ruhij jarayonlar va bola ruhiyatidagi o'zgarishlar, chunonchi, diqqat va xotira darajasi, tafakkur xususiyatlari so'z boyligi hamda nutqning rivojlanganlik darajasi va boshqalar ruhiy psixologik rivojlanishga ta'luqlidir. Bizning maktablarimizda ta'lim-tarbiya ishlari bolalarga faqat bilim berish bilan cheklanib qolmay, balki bolalarning barcha qobiliyatlarini o'stirishni nazarda tutgan holda olib boriladi.

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining intellektual salohiyatini rivojlanishida ularning tug'ma qobiliyat va iste'dodining o'rni muhim ahamiyatga ega. Tug'ma qobiliyatga ega bo'lgan yoshlarimiz kattalarning har bir ta'limiy, tarbiyaviy va kasbiy ta'limotlarini tez ilg'ab oladilar va tez o'zlashtirib hayotga tadbiiq eta oladilar. Lekin bu qobiliyat va iste'dod, barcha yoshlarimizga tug'ma talant nasib

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etavermaydi. Shunday ekan, qobiliyatni shakllantirib borish, yoshlarning iste'dodini oshirib borish birinchi navbatda pedagoglarimizga va keng jamoatchilik zimmasiga ya'ni oila, mahalla, o'quv muassasalari zimmasiga tushadi. Bolalar o'zidagi turli faoliyatlarga bo'lgan tug'ma layoqatlarni jamoada, o'z ustida tinmay ishlash jarayonida ro'yobga chiqaradilar. Maktablardagi sinf hamda jamoa, guruhlar, to'garaklar, fan olimpiadalarida ishtirok etish tug'ma layoqatlarning imkoniyatlaridir. Shuningdek, o'quv va mehnat faoliyatida bolalarning layoqatlari uyg'onadi va qobiliyatlari o'sadi. Iste'dod tushunchasining asosiy mazmuni «qobiliyat» degan tushunchani ham anglatadi.

Shuni aytish mumkinki, qobiliyat tushunchasini insonning tabiiy xususiyati deb qabul qilmay, biroq biz ko'p hollarda qobiliyat rivoji asosida ba'zi insonlarda tabiiy hususiyat, ya'ni iste'dod ham mavjudligini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Ba'zida «haqiqiy», «tabiiy», «tabiatdan berilgan» va shunga o'xshash so'zlar bilan aytilganda - «tabiiy» tushunchasi, - qobiliyat tushunchasi bilan amaliy tahlilda bir-biriga bog'liq. Ko'p hollarda biz tabiiylikni iste'dod rivoji asosida yotgan qobiliyatni tushunamiz. Balki kimdir biror joyda amaliy so'z ishlatishda, u yoki boshqa biror narsani - tabiiy xususiyatni qobiliyat deb ta'kidlashi mumkindir. Go'dak tug'ilgan vaqtda mavjud bo'lgan «garmonik his» yoki «musiqaga bo'lgan tuyg'u» haqida o'ylash dargumon. Ehtimol, har qanday idrokli inson, tug'ilgan daqiqadan boshlab, musiqaga bo'lgan tuyg'u yoki o'zaro his-tuyg'uning rivoji asosida faqat iste'dod nishonalari, qiziqish yoki shunga o'xshash tuyg'u mavjud deb o'ylash mumkin. Shuni alohida ta'kidlashimiz kerakki, tabiiy iste'dod nishonalari haqida gap ketganda, biz hali meros bo'lib qolgan iste'dod

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nishonalari haqida soʻzlaganimiz yoʻq.

Quyida yoshlarning intellektual ijodiy salohiyatini rivojlantirish usullaridan foydalanish haqida naʼmunalar keltiramiz:

Aql charhi mashqlarini oʻtkazish: bunga turli rebuslar, krasovordlar yechish, shaxmat va shashka oʻyinlarini musobaqa shaklida tashkil etish kiradi.

Yosh qalamkashlar toʻgaraklarini oʻtkazish: bunga yoshlarning ijodiy mahoratini, isteʼdodini oshirib borishga qaratilgan tadbirlari majmuasi kiradi. Masalan, yoshlar orasida yetishib chiqayotgan yozuvchi va jurnalistik mahoratga ega boʻlgan yoshlar bilan ishlash.

Chaqqonlar va epcillar sport oʻyinlarini oʻtkazish: bunga barcha turdagi sport musobaqalarini oʻtkazish kiradi.

Mushoira, gʻazalxonlik koʻrik tanlovlarini oʻtkazish: bu usulga yoshlarning sheʼr va gʻazallar orqali ijod qilishi kiradi. Bunga “Sheʼr kechasi” tadbirlarini oʻtkazish kiradi.

Quvnoqlar va zukkolar tanlovlarini oʻtkazish: bu tanlov orqali yoshlarning sanʼat, teatr va rassomchilikka boʻlgan qiziqishi orttiriladi va zukkolik mahorati baholanadi.

Ustoz-shorgird ishlarini takomillashtirish: bu usulni amalga oshirish uchun eng yaxshi ish olib borayotgan shogirdlari undan juda mamnun va minnatdor boʻlgan pedagog-ustozning ishlarini ommalashtiriladi.

Albatta yoshlarning ijodiy barcha ishlarini va isteʼdodli mahoratlarini baholash,

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ularni turli sovg'a va faxriy yorliqlar bilan mukofotlash maqsadga muvofiqdir.

Yuqorida keltirilgan nazariy holat va amaliy misollarga qaramay qobiliyat va uning rivojlanish muammosi psixologiya va pedagogikaning eng murakkab masalalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Qobiliyat sezgi analizatorlari, kuch, harakat hamda asabiy, jismoniy va aqliy jarayonlar muvofiqlashishi kabi nerv sistemasi xususiyatlariga bog'liq bo'lgan tabiiy iqtidor, iste'dod, shuningdek, tashqi ijtimoiy muhit ta'siri ostida rivojlanadi. Shuni ta'kidlash joizki, ijtimoiy muhitda ta'lim- tarbiyaga bolaning o'zi faol ishtirok etgandagina uning tug'ma layoqatini uyg'otadi, iste'dod, qobiliyatlarini o'stira oladi.

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari bilan munosabatda bo'lishda sabr-toqat, vazminlik zarur. Bolaning ijodiy imkoniyatlariga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadigan vaziyatli omillar quyidagilar:

- vaqt chegarasi;
- stress holati;
- yuqori tashvish holati;
- tezda yechim topish istagi;
- muayyan echim uchun qat'iy chegaralarning mavjudligi;
- oldingi muvaffaqiyatsizliklardan kelib chiqadigan ishonchsizlik;
- qo'rquv;

Ijodkor yoshlarni tarbiyalash jarayonida quyidagi holatlar yuzaga keladi:

1. Tarbiya yordamida muhitning salbiy ta'siri natijasida yuz bergan

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kamchiliklarni ham tugatish mumkin.

2. Tarbiya inson faoliyatining istiqbol maqsadini belgilaydi. Shu bois u shaxs kamolotini ta'minlashda yetakchi rol o'ynaydi.

3. Insonning ma'naviy o'sishi sodir bo'ladi, Masalan, bola o'z ona tilini atrofni o'rab turgan muhitning ta'sirida o'rganib olishi mumkin. Lekin o'qish va yozishni maxsus ta'lim yo'li bilangina o'rganadi. Ma'lum bilim, ko'nikma va malakalar faqat tarbiya jarayonida egallanadi.

4. Tarbiya yordamida hatto kishining ba'zi tug'ma kamchiliklarini ham ijobiy tomonga o'zgartirish mumkin. Chunonchi, ba'zi bir bolalar ayrim kamchiliklar bilan tug'iladi (kar, ko'r, soqov va hokazo). Lekin maxsus tashkil etilgan tarbiya yordamida ularning aqli to'la taraqqiy qiladi, tug'ma kamchiligi bo'lmagan kishilar bilan barobar faoliyatda bo'lishi mumkin.

Tabiiyki, o'quvchilarning o'z maqsadlariga erishishlari uchun ta'lim maskanida olgan bilim, ko'nikma va malakalari kamlik qiladi. Ular yuksak maqsad yo'lida o'z ustilarida tinmay izlanishlari, ijtimoiy munosabatlar jarayonida faol ishtirok etishlari lozim.

Fanlarda o'zlashtira olmagan o'quvchilarni qobiliyatsiz deyish xato, o'qituvchining birinchi galdagi vazifasi – har bir o'quvchining yosh va psixologik xususiyatini chuqur o'rganish, uning qiziqishi va istaklarini aniqlash, ularni hisobga olgan holda pedagogik chora-tadbirlarni ko'rishdir. Umuman, pedagogik jihatdan to'g'ri uyushtirilgan har qanday faoliyat bola shaxsining aqliy, axloqiy, estetik, jismoniy hamda irodaviy rivojlanishiga ijobiy ta'sir etadi.

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XULOSA

Bola shaxsining rivojlanishi uchun faol kundalik faoliyat zarur. Faoliyat yordamidagina bola atrof-muhit bilan munosabatni tashkil etadi, shu orqali uning bilish qobiliyati rivojlanadi, xarakter sifatлари takomillashib, kamol topadi.

Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ijodiy qobiliyatini rivojlantirishning ijtimoiy psixologik xususiyatlari qanday bo'ladi degan savolga biz quydagicha javob beramiz, tez va turli yo'llar bilan natijaga erishadi, o'zi qarorlar qabul qilishni o'rganadi va uni takomillashtiradi, o'zining salohiyati va ambitsiyalarini amalga oshiradi, o'qish sharoitlariga osonroq va to'liqroq moslashishadi, duch kelgan muammolarni hal qilishda moslashuvchan, aniq va samarali hal qila olish xususiyatlariga ega bo'ladi. Bola shaxsining ijodkor bo'lishiga o'qituvchi va murabbiylar sharoitlar yaratib berishi lozim, shunda jamiyatimizda yangi ixtirolar, innovatsiyalar paydo bo'ladi.

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